

Report: Ethiopian Space Science Society Dambi Dollo Branch Association Leaders

The Ethiopian Space Science Society Dambi Dollo Branch Association was founded in 2020 by 12 founders. Its present seven leaders are:

1. Abduselam Mohammed
2. Lamessa Fekede
3. Bulcha Bekele
4. Anatol Degafa
5. Dr. Leta Tesfaye
6. Arega Wakjira
7. Mulugeta Markos

The branch leaders contributed two scientific Presentation at ESSSGA-19 in the last July.

By: Abduselam Mohammed (Chair)
Dambi Dollo, Ethiopia
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